

Exploring The Diversity of Fungal Endophytes in Nine Medicinal Plant Species of Samba District, J&K, India

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Abstract

A total of 533 endophytic fungal isolates were obtained from leaf and stem tissues of nine medicinal plant species collected from the Samba District, J&K, India. These isolates belonged to four major taxonomic groups: Hyphomycetes, Ascomycetes, Coelomycetes, and sterile mycelia. Hyphomycetes constituted the dominant group, followed by Ascomycetes, Coelomycetes, and sterile forms. Isolation frequency analysis revealed that Hyphomycetes were significantly more abundant than other fungal classes ($p < 0.05$). In total, 18 fungal genera were recorded: *Alternaria*, *Aspergillus*, *Botrytis*, *Botryodiplodia*, *Curvularia*, *Phoma*, *Cladosporium*, *Cercospora*, *Phomopsis*, *Penicillium*, *Fusarium*, *Bipolaris*, *Emericella*, *Drechslera*, *Verticillium*, *Colletotrichum*, *Myrothecium*, and *Trichothecium*, showing broad distribution and strong association with host tissues. *Alternaria* sp., *Aspergillus fumigatus*, *Botrytis cinerea*, *Botryodiplodia* sp., *Cercospora* sp., *Cladosporium* sp., *Curvularia* sp., *Fusarium oxysporum*, and *Trichothecium roseum* were frequently occurred in all nine host. In contrast, *Phoma* sp., *Phomopsis* sp., *Verticillium* sp., and sterile mycelial isolates occurred less frequently.

Overall, the study reveals that medicinal plants such as *Phyllanthus emblica*, *Cassia fistula*, and *Terminalia arjuna* harbor rich and diverse endophytic fungal communities, whereas *Camphora officinarum*, *Cannabis sativa*, and *Achyranthes aspera* support lower diversity. The dominance of Hyphomycetes suggests their ecological success as endophytic colonizers in medicinal plants of the Samba region.

Keywords

Diversity, Fungal Endophytes, Medicinal Plant Species, Samba District,.

Introduction

Endophytes are microorganisms—including bacteria, fungi, and actinomycetes—that inhabit internal tissues of living plants without causing any immediate or visible disease symptoms (Bacon & White, 2000; Ajmeera & Vanteru, 2020). They have been reported from a broad range of plant groups, including algae (Hawksworth, 1988), lichens (Petrini et al., 1990; Suryanarayanan et al., 2005), mosses and other bryophytes (Petrini, 1986), ferns (Petrini et al., 1992), conifers (Giordano et al., 2009), and angiosperms (Arnold et al., 2000).

Objective of study

The present study investigates the diversity and distribution of fungal endophytes associated with nine medicinal plant species from the Samba District of Jammu and Kashmir, India. The objectives of this study were to investigate the diversity of endophytic fungi associated with leaf and stem tissues. This study contributes to a growing body of research on endophytic fungi from medicinal plants and provides baseline information on their ecological roles and potential for yielding novel bioactive compounds.

Review of Literature

Endophytic fungi are recognized as ubiquitous inhabitants of diverse ecosystems, including coastal mangroves (Kumaresan & Suryanarayanan, 2001), temperate evergreen forests (Espinosa-Garcia & Langenheim, 1990), xeric environments (Suryanarayanan et al., 2003), and tropical forests (Arnold et al., 2000). Their community structure is shaped by multiple ecological and biological factors such as host plant species (Saikkonen, 2007), geographical distances among host populations (Collado et al., 1999), and plant tissue type (Santamaria & Diez, 2005).

Medicinal plants are of special interest due to their production of diverse secondary metabolites such as alkaloids, terpenoids, and phenolics, which can influence the composition of their associated endophytic communities (Rai et al., 2014; Wen et al., 2022). Endophytic fungi isolated from medicinal plants have demonstrated the ability to synthesize bioactive compounds with antimicrobial, antiviral, anticancer, antifungal, and antioxidant activities, highlighting their biotechnological and pharmaceutical potential (Rodriguez et al., 2009; Hashem et al., 2023) Singh, V. K. and Kumar, A. (2023) ; Osman et.al 2025)

Methodology

Collection of plant sample

The survey was made for one year at Samba District, from healthy leaf, stem and bark samples of nine medicinal plant species (Table 2). The plant materials were collected in sterile polythene bags and brought to laboratory for the isolation of endophytic fungal isolates.

Isolation of endophytic fungi

Healthy, asymptomatic plant materials were carefully cleaned with running water and then surface sterilized using a modified Raviraja (2005) technique. After immersing the chosen leaf, stem, and bark segments in 95% ethanol for 30 seconds, 4% sodium hypochlorite solution for 60 seconds, and 95% ethanol for 30 seconds, they were rinsed three times for 10 seconds each with sterile distilled water and left to surface dry under sterile circumstances. After drying, each leaf segment was cut into approximately 0.5 cm squares and placed on Petri dishes containing Potato Dextrose Agar medium (PDA) supplemented with streptomycin (250µg/L) to suppress the bacterial growth. Petri dishes were sealed with Parafilm and incubated at 28±2°C in a light chamber for up to one week. The growth of endophytic fungal colonies was observed daily. Fresh PDA plates were then used to isolate the fungi that were emerging from the samples. The procedure of transferring isolates to fresh PDA plates was carried out several times in order to isolate pure colonies. All the fungal isolates were maintained in sterilized prepared media slants for preservation and identification. The endophytic fungal isolates were identified by using various keys and manual (Gilman, J.C. 1957; Ellis, M.B. 1971; Booth, C. 1971; Barron, G.L. 1972; Sutton, B.S. 1980).

Analysis

Statistical analysis

Colonization Frequency (CF%)

The colonization frequency (CF%) of a single endophytic fungal species in the leaf, stem and bark segments was calculated by using the following formula (Hata&Futai 1995)

Number of segments colonize by an endophytic fungal species

$$CF\% = \dots\dots\dots \times 100$$

Total number of segments

Relative percentage occurrence (RPO%) of each group of fungi

Relative percentage of occurrence (RPO%) of different group of fungi viz., Coelomycetes, Hyphomycetes, Ascomycetes and other sterile fungi was calculated using the following formula

Density of colonization of one fungal group

$$RPO\% = \dots\dots\dots \times 100$$

Total density of colonization of all fungal groups

Result and Discussion

A total of **533 endophytic fungal isolates** were obtained from leaf and stem tissues of **nine medicinal plant species**. These isolates belonged to four major taxonomic groups: **Hyphomycetes, Ascomycetes, Coelomycetes, and sterile mycelia**. In total, **18 fungal genera** were recovered, including *Alternaria*, *Aspergillus*, *Botrytis*, *Botryodiplodia*, *Curvularia*, *Phoma*, *Cladosporium*, *Cercospora*, *Phomopsis*, *Penicillium*, *Fusarium*, *Bipolaris*, *Emericella*, *Drechslera*, *Verticillium*, *Colletotrichum*, *Myrothecium*, and *Trichothecium* (table-1, table-3). These taxa showed wide distribution and strong association with medicinal plant tissues. Similar observation were made by (Rajagopal, K. and Suryanarayanan, T.S. 2000; Rajeshwari et al., 2017, Raviraja, N.S. 2005; Dhanalakshmi, et al., 2013; Barnabas et al. 2013; Naik, B.S., Krishnappa, M., and Krishnamurthy, Y.L. 2014) in various medicinal plants. The pie chart indicates that **endophytic fungal communities** are predominantly composed of **Hyphomycetes**, which account for **74%** of the total isolates, showing their major role as endophytes. **Coelomycetes** contribute **13%**, while **Ascomycetes** make up **9%**, reflecting moderate endophytic representation. **Sterile mycelium** forms the smallest group at **4%**, suggesting a limited presence among the endophytic fungi. Several fungi occurred consistently across hosts, indicating strong endophytic adaptation. The most frequently occurring species were *Alternaria sp.*, *Aspergillus fumigatus*, *Botrytis cinerea*, *Botryodiplodia sp.*, *Cercospora sp.*, *Cladosporium sp.*, *Curvularia sp.*, *Fusarium oxysporum*, and *Trichothecium roseum*. Among them, *Fusarium oxysporum* and *Botrytis cinerea* showed the strongest colonization ability and appeared across all evaluated parameters. Less frequent genera such as *Phoma sp.*, *Phomopsis*, *Verticillium sp.*, and sterile mycelia

appear to represent minor, possibly niche-specific endophytes (table-3). The diversity of endophytic fungi varied among the host plants studied. *Withania somnifera* showed the highest fungal diversity with all 21/21 fungi present. *Phyllanthus emblica* and *Cassia fistula* also supported high endophytic diversity, each harboring approximately 19/21 fungi. *Murraya koenigii* and *Terminalia arjuna* exhibited moderate diversity with about 15/21 fungi. In contrast, *Achyranthes aspera*, *Cannabis sativa*, and *Vinca rosea* showed lower diversity, while *Cinnamomum camphor* recorded the lowest endophytic fungal diversity with around 10/21 fungi present (table-3).

Endophytic fungal occurrence varied significantly among the nine medicinal plant hosts. **Hyphomycetes recorded the highest colonization levels** in both stem and leaf tissues. The greatest colonization was observed in *Amla (Phyllanthus emblica)*, with 7.9 % in stems and 7.7 % in leaves, followed by *Cassia fistula* (6.9 % stem, 5.8 % leaf) and *Terminalia arjuna* (6.8 % stem, 5.8 % leaf). **Coelomycetes** ranged only between 0.2–1.7% in stem, while **Ascomycetes were below 0.5%**, and sterile forms occurred rarely (table-4). Overall colonization rates revealed *Amla* as the richest host (10.1% stem, 9.2% leaf), followed by *Cassia fistula* (8.3 %, 7.7 %) and *Terminalia arjuna* (8.1%, 7.1%). The lowest colonization was recorded in *Camphora officinarum* (12% in both tissues) and *Cannabis sativa* (3.0% stem, 3.6% leaf) (table-4).

Diversity metrics supported these findings. The highest **Shannon diversity (H = 0.651)** and **Simpson diversity (1 - D = 0.338)** were recorded in *Cassia fistula*, indicating high richness and even species distribution. *Phyllanthus emblica* also showed high diversity (H = 0.589; 1 - D = 0.325). The lowest diversity was recorded in *Cannabis sativa* (H = 0.293; 1 - D = 0.157) and *Achyranthes aspera* (H = 0.294; 1 - D = 0.158), suggesting limited fungal diversity in these hosts.

Discussion

The dominance of **Hyphomycetes** among the 533 isolates is consistent with other studies showing that hyphomycetous fungi commonly prevail in endophytic communities — likely due to their rapid growth, efficient sporulation, and greater ability to colonize plant tissues under varied conditions. In contrast, the low frequencies of Ascomycetes, Coelomycetes, and sterile mycelial forms suggest these groups are either less competitive or require more specific environmental or physiological conditions to establish. Recovery of **18 fungal genera**, many of which (e.g., *Alternaria*, *Aspergillus*, *Fusarium*, *Curvularia*, *Cladosporium*) are frequently reported as endophytes, underlines the broad ecological adaptability of these fungi to medicinal plant tissues (Zou et al., 2000). In contrast, infrequent detection of genera like *Phoma*, *Phomopsis*, and *Verticillium* may indicate niche specialization or more stringent colonization requirements.

The variation in endophytic fungal diversity among host plants suggests that host species play a significant role in shaping endophyte communities. Plants like *Withania somnifera*, *Phyllanthus emblica*, and *Cassia fistula* may provide more favorable internal environments for fungal colonization, resulting in higher diversity. In contrast, lower diversity in plants such as *Cinnamomum camphor* and *Achyranthes aspera* may be influenced by host-specific biochemical or structural factors that limit endophyte establishment.

The striking variation in colonization and diversity among medicinal plants — with *Phyllanthus emblica*, *Cassia fistula*, *Terminalia arjuna*, and *Withania somnifera* hosting richer fungal communities, while *Camphora officinarum*, *Cannabis sativa*, and *Achyranthes aspera* supported few endophytes — suggests that **host traits (morphological, anatomical, biochemical)** strongly influence endophyte assemblages.

Finally, beyond mere colonization, endophytic fungi are increasingly recognized as potential producers of bioactive secondary metabolites with pharmaceutical and ecological significance (Hussain et al. 2024; Salmi et al., 2024). Thus, medicinal plants with high endophyte richness (like *Withania somnifera*, *Phyllanthus emblica*, *Cassia fistula*) represent promising reservoirs for novel bioactive fungi, whereas hosts with low diversity might harbor rare or specialized endophytes worthy of targeted study.

Table 1 Medicinal plant from which endophytic fungi were isolated

S.no	Plants	Habit	Family	Medicinal uses
1	<i>Achyranthes aspera</i>	herb	Amaranthaceae	Fever, Dysentery, Asthma, Scorpion and snake bites
2	<i>Cannabis sativa</i>	herb	Cannabaceae	Chronic pain, nausea and vomiting from chemotherapy, muscle spasms, anxiety, depression, some forms of epilepsy
3	<i>Cassia fistula</i>	tree	Fabaceae	Laxative, anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, and antimicrobial properties, used for skin issues, liver problems, fever, and constipation.
4	<i>Cinnamomum camphor</i>	tree	Lauraceae	used for pain relief, respiratory issues (coughs, congestion via inhalation), skin ailments, and as an insect repellent, with strong anti-inflammatory and analgesic properties
5	<i>Murraya koenigii</i>	tree	Rutaceae	Anti-inflammatory, Anti-cancer, Anti-diabetic, Anti-diarrheal, Anti-viral:
6	<i>Phyllanthus emblica</i>	tree	Phyllanthaceae	Kidney disease, improve blood fluidity, Immunity, Digestion
7	<i>Terminalia arjuna</i>	tree	combretaceae	Cardiovascular diseases (CVD), ulcers, diabetes, cough, excessive perspiration, asthma, tumor, inflammation and skin disorders.
8	<i>Vinca rosa</i>	herb	Apocynaceae	Used in cancer treatment, and traditional uses for diabetes, blood pressure, and wound healing.
9	<i>Withania somnifera</i>	herb	Solanceae	Neurodegenerative disorders, Arthritis, diabetes, epilepsy, and depression

Table 2. Fungal Genera Identified from the Medicinal Plants

Fungal Group	Genera Identified
Hyphomycetes	<i>Alternaria, Aspergillus, Penicillium, Fusarium, Cladosporium,</i>
	<i>Curvularia, Cercospora, Drechslera, Bipolaris, Verticillium Myrothecium, Botrytis</i>
Coelomycetes	<i>Botryodiplodia, Phoma, Phomopsis, Colletotrichum</i>
Ascomycetes	<i>Emericella</i>
Sterile mycelia	Unidentified sterile forms

Table 3: Frequency of Occurrence of Endophytic Fungi in Some Medicinal Plants

S. No.	Fungal species	Host plants									
		<i>Murraya koenigii</i>	<i>Withania somnifera</i>	<i>Terminalia arjuna</i>	<i>Vinca rosa</i>	<i>Achyranthes aspera</i>	<i>Cannabis sativa</i>	<i>Cinnamomum camphor</i>	<i>Phyllanthus emblica</i>	<i>Cassia fistula</i>	
1	<i>Alternaria sp</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	
2	<i>Aspergillus fumigate</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	
3	<i>Aspergillus nidulans</i>	-	+	-	+	+	-	-	+	+	
4	<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	+	+	+	-	+	-	-	+	+	
5	<i>Aspergillus terreus</i>	-	+	+	-	-	-	-	+	+	
6	<i>Bipolaris sp.</i>	-	+	+	-	-	-	-	+	+	
7	<i>Botryodiplodia sp.</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	
8	<i>Botrytis cinera</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	
9	<i>Cercospora sp</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	
10	<i>Cladosporium sp</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	
11	<i>Colletotrichum gloeosporioides</i>	-	+	+	-	-	-	-	+	-	
12	<i>Curvularia sp.</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	
13	<i>Drechslera sp.</i>	+	+	+	-	+	+	-	+	+	
14	<i>Emericella nidulans</i>	-	+	+	-	-	-	-	+	+	
15	<i>Fusarium oxysporum</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	
16	<i>Myrothecium sp</i>	+	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	+	
17	<i>Penicillium brevicompactum</i>	+	+	-	-	+	-	-	+	+	
18	<i>Phoma sp</i>	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	
19	<i>Phomopsis</i>	+	+	+	-	-	-	-	+	+	
20	<i>sterile mycelium</i>	+	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	+	
21	<i>Trichothecium roseum</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	
22	<i>Verticillium sp</i>	+	-	+	-	+	-	-	-	-	

+ = fungal species present ; - = fungal species absent

Chart Title

Table 4 - Percentage of Occurrence of Endophytic Fungi in Nine Medicinal Plants

S.No.	Host	Species (%age)								Percentage of Positive samples	
		Coelomycetes		Hyphomycetes		Ascomycetes		Sterile mycellium		stem	leaf
		stem	leaf	stem	leaf	stem	leaf	stem	leaf		
1	Muriaya koenigii	4(0.7)	4(0.7)	22(4.1)	20(3.8)	0	0	1(0.2)	1(0.2)	27(5.1)	25(4.7)
2	Withania somnifera	4(0.7)	2(0.4)	27(5.1)	28(5.3)	1(0.2)	0	1(0.2)	1(0.2)	33(6.2)	31(5.8)
3	Terminalia arjuna	4(0.7)	5(0.9)	36(6.8)	31(5.8)	2(0.2)	1(0.2)	1(0.2)	1(0.2)	43(8.1)	38(7.1)
4	Vinca rosa	2(0.4)	1(0.2)	18(3.4)	9(1.7)	0	0	0	1(0.2)	20(3.8)	11(2.1)
5	Achyranthes aspera	1(0.2)	4(0.7)	28(5.3)	25(4.7)	0	0	0	0	29(5.4)	29(5.4)
6	Cannabis sativa	1(0.2)	2(0.4)	15(2.8)	17(3.2)	0	0	0	0	16(3.0)	19(3.6)
7	Camphora officinarum	2(0.4)	2(0.4)	10(1.9)	10(1.9)	0	0	0	0	12(2.3)	12(2.3)
8	Phyllanthus emblica	9(1.7)	7(1.3)	42(7.9)	41(7.7)	3(0.5)	1(0.2)	0	0	54(10.1)	49(9.2)
9	Casia fistula	4(0.7)	8(1.5)	37(6.9)	31(5.8)	2(0.4)	2(0.2)	1(0.2)	0	44(8.3)	41(7.7)

Conclusion

The study demonstrates a clear dominance of **Hyphomycetes** among the 533 endophytic isolates recovered from nine medicinal plants, reflecting their superior capacity for colonization compared to Ascomycetes, Coelomycetes, and sterile mycelial forms. This pattern supports previous findings that hyphomycetous fungi are the most prevalent endophytes due to traits such as rapid growth and efficient sporulation. The presence of **18 fungal genera**, including commonly reported endophytes such as *Alternaria*, *Aspergillus*, *Fusarium*, and *Cladosporium*, highlights the strong adaptability of these taxa to internal plant tissues.

Endophytic diversity varied greatly among host species, with **Phyllanthus emblica**, **Cassia fistula**, **Terminalia arjuna**, and **Withania somnifera** supporting the richest fungal communities, while **Cannabis sativa**, **Camphora officinarum**, and **Achyranthes aspera** harbored fewer endophytes. These differences indicate that host anatomical and biochemical characteristics significantly determine endophyte colonization patterns.

Overall, the findings illustrate that endophytic fungal diversity in medicinal plants is shaped by a combination of **host species**, **tissue type**, **biochemical composition**, and **local environmental conditions**. The host specificity observed among several fungal groups suggests that plants exert selective pressures that favor or inhibit particular taxa. This supports the growing body of evidence that endophyte-plant interactions are dynamic and can vary widely depending on physiological and ecological factors (Arnold et al., 2003).

Significance of work

This study highlights the rich diversity of endophytic fungi in medicinal plants of the Samba District, J&K. It shows that Hyphomycetes are the dominant and most successful fungal endophytes, with several common genera widely associated with host plants. The findings improve understanding of plant-fungus interactions and provide a valuable baseline for future research on the ecological and biotechnological potential of endophytic fungi from medicinal plants.

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